

FATIGUE STRUCTURAL SUBSTANTIATION FOR THICK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A major barrier to rigorous failure predictions for polymer-matrix composites is the lack of measurements to quantify structural model parameters including matrix-dominated stress-strain relations and failure criteria. Accurate interlaminar constitutive properties are especially important for structural analysis of thick-section composites used in fixed-wing and rotary-wing fatigue-critical, flight-critical components and structure. In this work the interlaminar stress-strain relations and fatigue curves are generated for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional tape. The interlaminar constitutive properties are implemented in finite element-based failure models for multidirectional laminates with ply-waviness defects and subject to static and fatigue loads, to predict the onset of delamination. Failure predictions and subsequent test correlations are presented.

Keywords: Polymer-Matrix Composites, Stress-Strain Relations, Strength, Fatigue, Delamination, Failure Criteria.

INTRODUCTION

Accurate matrix-dominated constitutive properties can be a key to rigorous failure models for composite structures. Accurate interlaminar stress-strain relations and fatigue curves are especially important for structural analysis of thick-section composites. Examples of thick composite applications include rotor blade spar and blade-to-hub attachment structural details of rotary-wing aircraft [1]. Glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy tape materials are used for manufacturing such flight-critical structures.

A methodology for measurement of nonlinear interlaminar stress-strain relations for composites has been recently developed [2]. Such methodology is based on accurate full-field surface strain assessment using a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique. The main objectives of this work are: (a) to generate interlaminar constitutive properties including stress-strain relations and fatigue curves for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional tape; (b) to implement the interlaminar constitutive properties in ABAQUS finite element-based failure models of IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy multidirectional tape laminate articles subject to static and fatigue loading; and (c) to correlate the failure predictions with test data.

Figure 1. IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy Tape Wrinkle Coupons

An 88-ply $[(+45_3/0_2)_3/(+45_4/0_2)/(+45_4/0_4/+45_4)/(0_2/+45_4)/(0_2/+45_3)_3]_T$ IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy tape laminate with wavy plies is selected to verify the accuracy of the interlaminar failure models. Fiber waviness is a manufacturing defect oftentimes present in thick composites including rotorcraft parts [3]. Six tensile coupons were machined. The coupon thickness (laminate thickness) is 0.62 to 0.64 inches (15.7 to

16.3 mm); width is 0.14 inches (3.56 mm); length is 6 inches (3.6 mm) and gage (untabbed) length is 2.95 inches (74.9 mm). The first three coupons (B1, B2, B3) were subject to static load (0.05 inches/minute head displacement rate) and the remaining three coupons (B4, B5, B6) were subject to fatigue constant amplitude load at 10 Hz frequency and 0.1 load ratio, to delamination failure onset. Figure 1 shows the wavy (wrinkle) regions in the coupons.

The stress-strain relations for the failure models are presented in the following section.

STRESS-STRAIN RELATIONS

Table 1 lists linear material stiffness and strength data for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional tape [4]. Such data are used in the linear finite element-based failure models of the wrinkle coupons.

Table 1. IM7/8552 Tape Stiffness and Strength Properties

Tensile Moduli, GPa (msi)	
E_{11}	154 (22.3)
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	8.96 (1.3)
Shear Moduli, GPa (msi)	
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	5.31 (0.77)
G_{23}	2.96 (0.43)
Poisson's Ratio	
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.32
ν_{23}	0.5
Tensile Strength $S_{22} = S_{33}$, MPa (ksi)	98.6 (14.3)
Shear Strength $S_{12} = S_{13}$, MPa (ksi)	113 (16.4)

Transverse isotropic response is assumed. Fracture toughness-corrected tensile and shear strength S_{22} and S_{12} values available in open literature [5] are used.

Reference [4] also presents nonlinear interlaminar shear stress-strain properties for IM7/8552 unidirectional tape. To generate the interlaminar shear stress-strain response, eight 36-ply unidirectional tape short-beam shear (SBS) coupons, manufactured to ASTM Standard specifications [6], were statically loaded (0.05 inches/minute head displacement rate) in the (1,3) material plane to failure. The coupons are 1.5-inches-long (38.1 mm), 0.26-inches-thick (6.6 mm), and 0.2-inches-wide (5.1 mm). Support length is 1 inch (25.4 mm). The 0.2-inch width is smaller than the twice-the-thickness width recommended in the ASTM Standard [6] for more uniform interlaminar shear strain distribution through the width.

A Digital Image Correlations (DIC) full-field strain measurement technique was used for monitoring surface strains. The DIC strain measurement is based on quantifying locations of a random texture on specimen surface [7]. The random texture is generated using white and black spray-paints. A stereo digital camera set (white-light optics, no laser) is used to measure 3D surface shape and deformation. A commercially available DIC tool VIC-3D [8] was utilized.

Figure 2 shows a SBS test setup and a shear strain measurement.

Figure 2. SBS Test Setup and Full-Field Strain Measurement

Figure 3 shows the interlaminar shear stress-strain response in the (1,3) material plane for the eight coupons tested.

Figure 3. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Shear Stress-Strain Response for Eight Unidirectional IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy Tape SBS Specimens [4]

The methodology for assessment of the shear stress-strain response is listed in Ref. [2]. A closed-form shear stress approximation [2] was used. Ramberg-Osgood equations [2]

$$\gamma_{13} = \frac{\tau_{13}}{G_{13}} + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{K} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (1)$$

fit the test data using a least squares approximation. Table 2 lists the average values (AVG) and the coefficients of variation (COV) for the interlaminar shear strength S_{13} corresponding to the ultimate failure load, and linear shear modulus G_{13} , secant-intercept modulus K , and exponent n .

Table 2. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Shear Strength and Stiffness Values

	AVG	COV
S_{13} , MPa (ksi)	113.8 (16.5)	1.59%
G_{13} , MPa (ksi)	5.48 (0.795)	5.57%
K , MPa (ksi)	261 (37.8)	5.38%
n	0.203	6.26%

It is worth noting that the linear shear modulus G_{13} and shear strength S_{13} values listed in Table 2 are similar to G_{12} and S_{12} values in Ref. [5].

FATIGUE CONSTITUTIVE PROPERTIES

S-N curves for initiation of shear and tensile delaminations in the unidirectional IM7/8552 tape are presented in this section.

Figure 4. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Shear S-N Curve for Unidirectional IM7/8552 Tape

To generate the interlaminar shear fatigue curve, constant load amplitude SBS fatigue tests at 0.1 load ratio and 10 Hz frequency were conducted. A shear fatigue delamination failure close to the mid-surface of the coupons could not be obtained using the static SBS test coupon dimensions. Matrix compressive damage under the loading nose of the test fixture resulted in delamination close to the coupon upper surface. To reduce the compressive loads, the dimensions of the fatigue SBS test coupons used in this work were modified to 0.15 inch thickness (3.8 mm), 0.12 inch width (3.0 mm), and 0.76 inch length (19.3 mm). The loading nose roller diameter in the ASTM Standard D 2344 SBS test fixture was also modified from 0.25 inches (6.35 mm) to 0.5 inches (12.7 mm). A shear delamination was established for all fatigue SBS tests except one that took close to 10 million cycles to delamination onset.

Figure 4 shows the interlaminar shear stress at peak loads as a function of cycles to delamination onset. A power law

$$\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}} = 1.2487(\log N)^{-0.4123} \quad (2)$$

approximates the average response based on a linear regression. Five static SBS tests were also conducted to confirm the constitutive properties for the modified SBS test configuration. Table 3 lists the static strength and stiffness parameters.

Table 3. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Shear Strength and Stiffness Values for the Modified SBS Test Configuration

	AVG	COV
S_{13} , MPa (ksi)	110 (16)	2%
G_{13} , MPa (ksi)	5.32 (0.771)	4%
K , MPa (ksi)	247 (35.8)	4.86%
n	0.208	4.95%

Curved-Beam Test Setup

Transverse Tensile Strain

Figure 5. Curved-Beam Test Set-up and Full-Field Strain Measurement

The interlaminar tensile constitutive properties were generated based on curved-beam tests. Five static and six fatigue unidirectional IM7/8552 tape curved-beam coupons were tested. The coupons were manufactured to ASTM Standard specifications [9],

except the width was reduced from 1 inch (25.4 mm) to 0.5 inches (12.7 mm). The curved-beam coupons are 0.26-inches-thick (6.6 mm). Figure 5 shows a curved-beam test setup and a transverse tensile strain measurement.

The DIC technique was used for assessment of surface strain. A closed-form solution [9] was used for interlaminar stress approximation.

The failure mode for the curved-beam test coupons was a tensile delamination. The interlaminar tensile stress-strain response was linear till failure. The average value for the interlaminar tensile modulus E_{33} is 1.3 msi (8.96 GPa) and the coefficient of variation is 3.55%. The average value for the curved-beam interlaminar tensile strength S_{33} is 12 ksi (82.7 MPa) and the coefficient of variation is 7.78%.

To generate the interlaminar tensile fatigue curve, constant load amplitude curved-beam tests at 0.1 load ratio and 5 Hz frequency were conducted. Figure 6 shows the interlaminar tensile stress at peak loads as a function of cycles to delamination onset.

Figure 6. Interlaminar (1-3 Plane) Tensile S-N Curve for Unidirectional IM7/8552 Tape

A power law

$$\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}} = 0.9001(\log N)^{-0.3504} \quad (3)$$

approximates the average fatigue behavior. Equations (2) and (3) are used to predict fatigue delamination onset in the wrinkle coupons based on failure criteria listed in the

next section.

FATIGUE FAILURE CRITERIA

The basic material S-N curves (2) and (3) are used in matrix-dominated failure criteria which account for the presence of interlaminar tensile and shear stresses, to predict the number of cycles to fatigue delamination in the wrinkle test coupons. The following criteria are applied:

The Hashin Mixed-mode strength criterion [10]

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 &= 1, \quad \sigma_{33} > 0 \\ \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 &= 1, \quad \sigma_{33} \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and a Fracture toughness-based criterion [11]

$$\begin{aligned} (1-g)\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}} + g\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{S_{33}}\right)^2 + \frac{\chi(\tau_{13})}{\chi(S_{13})} &= 1, \quad \sigma_{33} > 0 \\ \frac{\chi(\tau_{13})}{\chi(S_{13})} &= 1, \quad \sigma_{33} \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $g = G_{Ic} / G_{IIc}$, and G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} are Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness values and $\chi(\tau_{13})$ is a shear component of the strain energy density

$$\chi(\tau_{13}) = 2 \int \tau_{13} d\gamma_{13}(\tau_{13})$$

For the non-linear shear response (1) this function is integrated as follows [12]

$$\chi(\tau_{13}) = \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{G_{13}} + \frac{2K}{n+1} \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{K}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}+1} \quad (6)$$

The interlaminar shear and tensile strength values in the fatigue failure criteria are assumed to follow the material S-N curves (2) and (3)

$$\begin{aligned} S_{33} &= S_{33,static} 0.9001(\log N)^{-0.3504} \\ S_{13} &= S_{13,static} 1.2487(\log N)^{-0.4123} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $S_{33,static}$ and $S_{13,static}$ are static interlaminar tensile and shear strengths. A constant mixed-mode ratio $g = 0.3521$ calculated from the mean fracture toughness values in

Ref. [5] is assumed as the available fatigue data for the Mode II energy release rate component exhibit large scatter [15].

To calculate the number of cycles to failure in a finite element-based model, Equations (7) are substituted in the failure criteria (4) and (5) to calculate the cycles to failure for each element. The minimum number of cycles corresponds to structural failure.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

Plane stress finite element-based failure models were built for the static and fatigue wrinkle coupons in ABAQUS software [13]. The wavy-ply geometry for the finite element models was generated using digital images of the coupons. The JPEG images were loaded in the Matlab software. A Matlab script was developed to determine the ply-interfaces based on the pixel gray value intensities. Then an ABAQUS Python script was developed to create the wrinkle geometry partitions based on spline interpolation of ply-interfaces. Figure 7 shows the finite element mesh for the static wrinkle coupons in the wavy regions and Figure 11 shows a zoom-in view in the wavy region. The finite element models include about 100,000 4-node plane stress elements CPS4R and 200,000 DOF for each coupon.

Figure 7. Plane Stress Finite Element Mesh for Static Wrinkle Coupons

The zero-degree plies are shown in green color and the ± 45 -degree plies are shown in red. Table 1 lists the linear stiffness and interlaminar strength data, and Table 2 lists the parameters for the nonlinear interlaminar shear stress-strain response of IM7/8552 unidirectional tape. The 1-3 plane material properties listed in the Tables 1 and 2 are used for modeling of the 0-degree ply-groups. The ± 45 -degree ply-groups are represented in the finite element models through effective plane-stress stiffness

properties in the wavy-ply local axial and through-the-thickness coordinates. A coordinate transformation for 3D stiffness tensor components [14] is used to obtain the linear stiffness constants for the ± 45 -degree plies. A ratio of the effective transverse shear modulus for ± 45 -degree plies and G_{13} shear modulus for 0-degree plies scales the nonlinear shear stress-strain response for the ± 45 -degree plies.

The nonlinear interlaminar shear stress-strain relations were implemented in ABAQUS through a user subroutine UMAT [13] by providing local stresses response and stress-strain Jacobian for each finite element. To obtain the stress response, Equation (1) is discretized at equal strain intervals and the resulting stress-strain table is used for interpolation.

Figure 8. Interlaminar Strain (Local Material Directions) Contour Plots for Wrinkle Coupon B1 at 18802 N (4227 lbs) Tensile Load just Before Failure

The damage indices for static and fatigue failure predictions are also calculated in the user subroutine based on Equations (4-5). The indices are stored as ABAQUS state variables and visualized in the Matlab script. Fatigue failure predictions are based on solving non-linear algebraic equations for the two failure criteria using the Newton-Raphson method. The interlaminar tensile and shear strength values are used for initial

guess selection. Since the first derivative of the failure criteria functions with respect to Log of the cycles to failure N is positive for $N > 1$, the algebraic equations have only a single root. The elements with stresses less than 15% of respective strengths are assumed not to fail to avoid numerical overflow.

FINITE ELEMENT-BASED STATIC FAILURE PREDICTIONS

Three wrinkle coupons B1, B2, and B3 were statically loaded to failure. The DIC technique was used to monitor surface strains. Delaminations for all coupons occur at the largest wrinkle between $[\pm 45]_4$ and $[0]_4$ ply-groups. Figures 8 – 10 show the nonlinear finite element predictions and test data for the interlaminar strain (material directions) contour plots for the wrinkle coupons just before delamination.

Figure 9. Interlaminar Strain (Local Material Directions) Contour Plots for Wrinkle Coupon B2 at 15764 N (3544) lbs Tensile Load just Before Failure

Figure 10. Interlaminar Strain (Local Material Directions) Contour Plots for Wrinkle Coupon B3 at 18223 N (4097 lbs) Tensile Load just Before Failure

Table 4 compares the finite element-based failure load predictions based on the Hashin failure criterion and test data corresponding to delamination onset.

Table 4. Finite Element-Based Failure Load Predictions and Test Data

Test	Linear FEM	Nonlinear FEM	Test Data
B1	13615 N (3061 lbs) Error: -28%	16378 N (3682 lbs) Error: -13%	18895 N (4248 lbs)
B2	12050 N (2709 lbs) Error: -24%	14941 N (3359 lbs) Error: -5%	15790 N (3550 lbs)
B3	13460 N (3026 lbs) Error: -26%	17369 N (3905 lbs) Error: -5%	18241 N (4101 lbs)

The interlaminar strain and failure load predictions and measurements are in agreement. The failure locations were also captured. Figure 11 shows the finite element-based mixed-mode (Hashin) damage index for coupon B2 at 15790 N (3550 lbs) tensile load corresponding to the delamination onset.

Figure 11. Delamination Location Predictions and Test Data for Wrinkle Coupon B2 at 15790 N (3550 lbs) Tensile Load

The damage index values higher than one indicate delamination initiation at two locations in agreement with test.

FINITE ELEMENT-BASED FATIGUE FAILURE PREDICTIONS

This section compares the finite element-based fatigue failure predictions and test data for wrinkle coupons. Three coupons B4, B5, and B6 were subject to constant amplitude loads at 10 Hz frequency and 0.1 load ratio, to delamination failure onset. Table 5 lists maximum loads and compares the cycles to delamination onset.

Table 5. Finite Element-Based Predictions and Test Data for Cycles to Failure

Test	Load	Hashin (4)	Fracture (5)	Test Data
B4	9875 N (2200 lbs)	3,800,000	710,000	750,000
B5	8674 N (1950 lbs)	700	600	≤1,000
B6	6894 N (1550 lbs)	225,000	93,000	50,000 (first onset) 130,000 (second onset)

The DIC technique was used to monitor the peak strains at 500-cycle intervals during fatigue loading. A clear visible delamination onset was detected in the B4 and B5 wrinkle coupons. For the B6 coupon, the onset was not detectable in the individual images but traceable though a slight shift in the speckle pattern during a movie replay of the images.

Figures 12, 14 and 16 show fatigue delamination onset. Figures 13, 15 and 17 show the damage indices for the failure criteria (4) and (5).

Figure 12. Fatigue Delamination Location for Coupon B4

Figure 13. Damage Indices for Coupon B4 at the Predicted Cycles to Failure using the Hashin (Left) and Fracture Toughness-Based (Right) Failure Criteria

Figure 14. Fatigue Delamination Location for Coupon B5

Figure 15. Damage Indices for Coupon B5 at the Predicted Cycles to Failure using the Hashin (Left) and Fracture Toughness-Based (Right) Failure Criteria

Figure 16. Fatigue Delamination Locations for Coupon B6

Figure 17. Damage Indices for Coupon B6 at the Predicted Cycles to Failure using the Hashin (Left) and Fracture Toughness-Based (Right) Failure Criteria

The damage index equal to one corresponds to delamination initiation. The damage index contour plots for the B4 coupon are similar to the interlaminar tensile strain pattern (Figures 8 through 10). The damage index contour plots for the B5 and B6 coupons are similar to the interlaminar shear strain patterns.

Although the finite element models agree with the test data for cycles to failure, fatigue delaminations are shifted from the main wrinkles (FEM) to the secondary wrinkles (tests). One reason could be ply-terminations in the ± 45 -degree ply-groups at failure-critical locations. Figure 18 shows ply-terminations in the B4 coupon.

Figure 18. Ply-terminations in ± 45 -Degree Ply-Groups for Coupon B4

The finite element models presented in this work do not account for such discontinuities. Also, accurate interlaminar constitutive properties for the ± 45 -degree ply-groups must be determined based on the SBS and curved-beam tests.

CONCLUSIONS

Basic material-scale constitutive properties generated for IM7/8552 Carbon/Epoxy unidirectional tape are implemented in finite element-based failure models to predict delamination onset in a thick multidirectional laminate with wavy plies subject to static and fatigue tension. The failure predictions are subsequently correlated with tests. The nonlinear interlaminar shear stress-strain response enables accurate static failure predictions for the wrinkle laminates. The basic material S-N fatigue curves are used with mixed-mode failure criteria to predict fatigue delamination. The finite element-based fatigue failure predictions and test data show similar trend and encourage further model development and test correlations for the methodology verification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Dobyms, A., Rousseau, C. Q., and Minguet, P. (2000). Helicopter Applications and Design, *Delaware Composites Design Encyclopedia*, Vol. 5, 223-242.
- [2] Makeev, A., Ignatius, C., He, Y., and Shonkwiler, B. (2009). A Test Method for Assessment of Shear Properties for Thick Composites, accepted for publication in the *Journal of Composite Materials*.
- [3] Murri, G. (1999). Influence of Ply Waviness on Fatigue Life of Tapered Composite Flexbeam Laminates, ASTM Symposium on Composite Structures: Theory and Practice, Seattle, WA
- [4] Makeev, A., Seon, G., and Lee, E. (2009) Failure Predictions for Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminates with Wavy Plies, accepted for publication in the *Journal of Composite Materials*.
- [5] Camanho, P. P. and Lambert, M. (2006). A Design Methodology for Mechanically Fastened Joints in Laminated Composite Materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, 66(15), 3004-3020.
- [6] American Society for Testing and Materials (2006). Standard Test Method for Short-Beam Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials and Their Laminates, ASTM Standard D 2344/D 2344M, ASTM International.
- [7] Peng, C., Sutton, M. A., Shreier, H. W., and McNeill, S. R. (2002). Full-Field Speckle Pattern Image Correlation with B-Spline Deformation Function, *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 49, 344-352.
- [8] www.correlatedsolutions.com

- [9] American Society for Testing and Materials (2006). Standard Test Method for Measuring the Curved Beam Strength of a Fiber-Reinforced Polymer-Matrix Composite, ASTM Standard D 6415/D 6415M, ASTM International.
- [10] Hashin, Z. (1980). Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 47, 329–334.
- [11] Camanho, P. P., Davila, C. G., Pinho, S. T., Iannucci, L., and Robinson, P. (2006). Prediction of in situ strengths and matrix cracking in composites under transverse tension and in-plane shear, *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 37, 165–176.
- [12] Nikishkov, Y., Makeev, A., and Seon, G. (2009). Finite Element-Based Simulations of Damage in Composites, *Proceedings of the American Helicopter Society 65th Forum*.
- [13] ABAQUS 6.8.1. User's Manual (2008). ABAQUS Inc., Pawtucket, RI, USA.
- [14] Lekhnitskii, S. G. (1981). *Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Body*, Mir Publishers, Moscow.
- [15] Hansen, P. and Martin R. (1999). DCB, 4ENF and MMB Delamination Characterization of S2/8552 and IM7/8552, Final Technical Report, US Army Contract Number N68171-98-M-5177, EUROPEAN RESEARCH OFFICE OF THE US ARMY, London, England.